

DIAGONAL ZETA IDENTITIES FOR THE BEUKERS–APÉRY ARRAY

ALEX SHVETS

ABSTRACT. We prove a family of diagonal identities for the two-variable Beukers–Apéry array

$$T(n, k) = \sum_{j=0}^n \binom{n+j}{2j} \binom{2j}{j}^2 \binom{k+j}{2j}.$$

For every integer $k \geq 0$ we show that

$$\zeta(3) = \sum_{m=1}^k \frac{1}{m^3} + \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{(2n+k)(3n^2+3nk+k^2)}{n^3(n+k)^3 T(n-1, n+k-1) T(n, n+k)}.$$

The case $k = 0$ gives the classical main-diagonal identity, and the cases $k \geq 1$ prove the corresponding shifted-diagonal identities. The proof is elementary. Its main input is a contiguous relation for the array $T(n, k)$, proved by an explicit finite hypergeometric telescoping certificate. This relation makes a natural discrete one-form closed; the diagonal series is then transformed by path deformation into the tail of the ordinary series for $\zeta(3)$.

1. STATEMENT

Throughout the paper we use the convention

$$\binom{a}{b} = 0 \quad \text{if } b < 0 \text{ or } b > a$$

for nonnegative integers a, b . Define the two-variable array

$$(1) \quad T(n, k) = \sum_{j=0}^n \binom{n+j}{2j} \binom{2j}{j}^2 \binom{k+j}{2j} \quad (n, k \geq 0).$$

Because of the binomial convention the sum is effectively finite up to $j \leq \min(n, k)$. The definition is symmetric in n, k , so

$$(2) \quad T(n, k) = T(k, n).$$

The main diagonal $T(n, n)$ is the classical Apéry sequence attached to $\zeta(3)$.

The result proved here is the following shifted-diagonal identity.

Theorem 1.1. *For every integer $k \geq 0$,*

$$(3) \quad \zeta(3) = \sum_{m=1}^k \frac{1}{m^3} + \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{(2n+k)(3n^2+3nk+k^2)}{n^3(n+k)^3 T(n-1, n+k-1) T(n, n+k)}.$$

The finite sum is understood to be 0 when $k = 0$.

For $k = 0$, formula (3) becomes

$$(4) \quad \zeta(3) = 6 \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{n^3 T(n-1, n-1) T(n, n)}.$$

For $k = 1$ it becomes

$$(5) \quad \zeta(3) = 1 + \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{(2n+1)(3n^2+3n+1)}{n^3(n+1)^3 T(n-1, n) T(n, n+1)}.$$

2. A CONTIGUOUS RELATION

The proof rests on one finite hypergeometric identity. We present it in a form that keeps all boundary terms explicit.

Lemma 2.1 (Two-variable contiguous relation). *For all $a, b \geq 0$, with*

$$x = a + 1, \quad y = b + 1,$$

one has

$$(6) \quad x^3 T(a+1, b+1) + y^3 T(a, b) = (x+y)(x^2 + xy + y^2) T(a, b+1),$$

and, by symmetry,

$$(7) \quad y^3 T(a+1, b+1) + x^3 T(a, b) = (x+y)(x^2 + xy + y^2) T(a+1, b).$$

Proof. It is enough to prove (6); the second identity follows by interchanging a and b and using (2).

Set $x = a + 1$, $y = b + 1$, and

$$R = (x+y)(x^2 + xy + y^2).$$

For $j \geq 0$ define

$$\begin{aligned} A_j &= \binom{x+j}{2j} \binom{2j}{j}^2 \binom{y+j}{2j}, \\ B_j &= \binom{x+j-1}{2j} \binom{2j}{j}^2 \binom{y+j-1}{2j}, \\ C_j &= \binom{x+j-1}{2j} \binom{2j}{j}^2 \binom{y+j}{2j}. \end{aligned}$$

Thus

$$\sum_{j \geq 0} A_j = T(a+1, b+1), \quad \sum_{j \geq 0} B_j = T(a, b), \quad \sum_{j \geq 0} C_j = T(a, b+1).$$

All sums are finite under the binomial convention.

For $j \geq 1$ put

$$(8) \quad G_j = -\frac{j^2(x+y)}{2} \binom{x+j-1}{2j-1} \binom{2j}{j}^2 \binom{y+j-1}{2j-1},$$

and set $G_0 = 0$. Then $G_j = 0$ for all sufficiently large j . A direct simplification gives the finite telescoping identity

$$(9) \quad x^3 A_j + y^3 B_j - RC_j = G_{j+1} - G_j \quad (j \geq 0).$$

For completeness we indicate the verification. If

$$C_j = \binom{x+j-1}{2j} \binom{2j}{j}^2 \binom{y+j}{2j},$$

then

$$\begin{aligned}\frac{A_j}{C_j} &= \frac{x+j}{x-j}, \\ \frac{B_j}{C_j} &= \frac{y-j}{y+j}, \\ \frac{C_{j+1}}{C_j} &= \frac{(j+1-x)(j+x)(j-y)(j+y+1)}{(j+1)^4},\end{aligned}$$

where these identities are interpreted after cancellation; equivalently one may use (8), which is polynomial-binomial and has no pole. Substituting these three ratios into (9) reduces it to the rational identity

$$\begin{aligned}x^3 \frac{x+j}{x-j} + y^3 \frac{y-j}{y+j} - R \\ = -\frac{2(j+1)^4(x+y)}{(x-j-1)(y+j+1)} \frac{(j+1-x)(j+x)(j-y)(j+y+1)}{(j+1)^4} + \frac{2j^4(x+y)}{(x-j)(y+j)},\end{aligned}$$

which expands to an identity in x, y, j .

Summing (9) over $j \geq 0$ gives

$$x^3 T(a+1, b+1) + y^3 T(a, b) - RT(a, b+1) = \sum_{j \geq 0} (G_{j+1} - G_j) = 0,$$

because $G_0 = 0$ and $G_j = 0$ for all sufficiently large j . This proves (6). \square

3. A CLOSED DISCRETE ONE-FORM

We now translate the contiguous relation into path independence on the integer lattice. For a horizontal edge

$$(a, b-1) \longrightarrow (a, b) \quad (b \geq 1)$$

define

$$(10) \quad H(a, b) = \frac{1}{b^3 T(a, b-1) T(a, b)}.$$

For a vertical edge

$$(a-1, b) \longrightarrow (a, b) \quad (a \geq 1)$$

define

$$(11) \quad V(a, b) = \frac{1}{a^3 T(a-1, b) T(a, b)}.$$

Lemma 3.1 (Closedness around an elementary square). *For all $a, b \geq 0$,*

$$(12) \quad H(a, b+1) + V(a+1, b+1) = V(a+1, b) + H(a+1, b+1).$$

Proof. Let

$$A = T(a, b), \quad B = T(a, b+1), \quad C = T(a+1, b), \quad D = T(a+1, b+1),$$

and again put $x = a+1$, $y = b+1$, and

$$R = (x+y)(x^2 + xy + y^2).$$

By Lemma 2.1,

$$(13) \quad x^3 D + y^3 A = RB,$$

and

$$(14) \quad y^3 D + x^3 A = RC.$$

Therefore

$$\begin{aligned} H(a, b+1) + V(a+1, b+1) &= \frac{1}{y^3 AB} + \frac{1}{x^3 BD} \\ &= \frac{x^3 D + y^3 A}{x^3 y^3 ABD} \\ &= \frac{R}{x^3 y^3 AD}, \end{aligned}$$

while

$$\begin{aligned} V(a+1, b) + H(a+1, b+1) &= \frac{1}{x^3 AC} + \frac{1}{y^3 CD} \\ &= \frac{y^3 D + x^3 A}{x^3 y^3 ACD} \\ &= \frac{R}{x^3 y^3 AD}. \end{aligned}$$

The two expressions agree, proving (12). \square

Thus the edge weights (10) and (11) define a closed discrete one-form on the first quadrant of the integer lattice.

4. DIAGONAL STEPS

The summand in Theorem 1.1 is exactly the weight of a diagonal step, computed as the sum of one horizontal and one vertical edge.

Lemma 4.1 (Diagonal edge weight). *Fix $k \geq 0$. For every $n \geq 1$,*

$$(15) \quad \begin{aligned} &H(n-1, n+k) + V(n, n+k) \\ &= \frac{(2n+k)(3n^2 + 3nk + k^2)}{n^3(n+k)^3 T(n-1, n+k-1) T(n, n+k)}. \end{aligned}$$

Proof. Apply (6) with

$$a = n-1, \quad b = n+k-1, \quad x = n, \quad y = n+k.$$

Then

$$x^3 T(n, n+k) + y^3 T(n-1, n+k-1) = (x+y)(x^2 + xy + y^2) T(n-1, n+k).$$

Using this identity,

$$\begin{aligned} &H(n-1, n+k) + V(n, n+k) \\ &= \frac{1}{(n+k)^3 T(n-1, n+k-1) T(n-1, n+k)} + \frac{1}{n^3 T(n-1, n+k) T(n, n+k)} \\ &= \frac{n^3 T(n, n+k) + (n+k)^3 T(n-1, n+k-1)}{n^3(n+k)^3 T(n-1, n+k-1) T(n-1, n+k) T(n, n+k)} \\ &= \frac{(2n+k)(n^2 + n(n+k) + (n+k)^2)}{n^3(n+k)^3 T(n-1, n+k-1) T(n, n+k)} \\ &= \frac{(2n+k)(3n^2 + 3nk + k^2)}{n^3(n+k)^3 T(n-1, n+k-1) T(n, n+k)}. \end{aligned}$$

□

5. PROOF OF THE MAIN THEOREM

Let $k \geq 0$ be fixed. For $N \geq 1$ define the partial diagonal sum

$$(16) \quad S_N(k) = \sum_{n=1}^N \frac{(2n+k)(3n^2+3nk+k^2)}{n^3(n+k)^3 T(n-1, n+k-1) T(n, n+k)}.$$

By Lemma 4.1, this is the sum of the closed one-form along the staircase path

$$(0, k) \rightarrow (0, k+1) \rightarrow (1, k+1) \rightarrow (1, k+2) \rightarrow \cdots \rightarrow (N, N+k).$$

By Lemma 3.1, the value of the sum is unchanged if the staircase path is replaced by the path that first moves horizontally from $(0, k)$ to $(0, N+k)$ and then vertically from $(0, N+k)$ to $(N, N+k)$. Therefore

$$(17) \quad S_N(k) = \sum_{m=k+1}^{N+k} \frac{1}{m^3} + \sum_{r=1}^N \frac{1}{r^3 T(r-1, N+k) T(r, N+k)}.$$

Indeed, $T(0, m) = 1$ for all $m \geq 0$, so the horizontal part is exactly the first sum.

It remains to show that the vertical remainder tends to zero. Put

$$B = N + k.$$

The first vertical term is

$$\frac{1}{T(0, B) T(1, B)} = \frac{1}{1 + 2B(B+1)} = O(B^{-2}),$$

since $T(0, B) = 1$ and $T(1, B) = 1 + 2B(B+1)$. For $r \geq 2$, the $j = 1$ term in (1) gives

$$T(r, B) \geq r(r+1)B(B+1), \quad T(r-1, B) \geq (r-1)rB(B+1).$$

Consequently,

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{r=2}^N \frac{1}{r^3 T(r-1, B) T(r, B)} &\leq \frac{1}{B^2(B+1)^2} \sum_{r=2}^{\infty} \frac{1}{r^5 (r-1)(r+1)} \\ &= O(B^{-4}). \end{aligned}$$

Thus the second sum in (17) tends to zero as $N \rightarrow \infty$. Passing to the limit in (17) gives

$$\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{(2n+k)(3n^2+3nk+k^2)}{n^3(n+k)^3 T(n-1, n+k-1) T(n, n+k)} = \sum_{m=k+1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{m^3}.$$

Therefore

$$\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{(2n+k)(3n^2+3nk+k^2)}{n^3(n+k)^3 T(n-1, n+k-1) T(n, n+k)} = \zeta(3) - \sum_{m=1}^k \frac{1}{m^3},$$

which is precisely (3). The theorem is proved.

6. COMMENTS

The proof shows that the shifted-diagonal identities are consequences of a closed discrete one-form. The diagonal summand is not isolated; it is the value of the form on a two-edge staircase step. Since the form is closed, the diagonal path may be moved to the boundary of the quadrant, where it becomes the elementary tail of $\sum_{m \geq 1} m^{-3}$. This explains why the same value $\zeta(3)$ appears on every shifted diagonal.

REFERENCES

- [1] R. Apéry, *Irrationalité de $\zeta(2)$ et $\zeta(3)$* , Astérisque **61** (1979), 11–13.
- [2] F. Beukers, *A note on the irrationality of $\zeta(2)$ and $\zeta(3)$* , Bull. London Math. Soc. **11** (1979), no. 3, 268–272.
- [3] N. J. A. Sloane et al., *The On-Line Encyclopedia of Integer Sequences*, entry A143007, <https://oeis.org/A143007>.